

The ABCs of Psychometric Validity: A Practical Guide for English Language Teachers

Talia Isaacs¹

UCL Institute of Education, University College London

ABSTRACT

This article offers an accessible discussion of assessment literacy and validity in the context of language testing and assessment practice. Assessment literacy can be broadly defined as the skills and knowledge teachers have about the functions and roles of assessment in educational contexts. It is also related to the ability to choose various forms of assessment to serve an intended purpose, as well as an awareness of critical assessment-related issues, such as validity, fairness, ethics, and the effects of assessment on students and other stakeholders. This article relates assessment literacy to the concept of psychometric validity, which can help English language teachers evaluate their own and others' assessment practices through explicit and practical guides. Validity is a complex concept that requires clear explanations and examples tailored for teachers. Through this article, readers can enhance their understanding of core assessment concepts and learn how to implement positive assessment practices.

¹ Correspondence: Talia Isaacs (talia.isaacs@ucl.ac.uk); <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4302-3379>

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INTRODUCTION

National educational reform is a global phenomenon. One of governments' national strategic priorities is economic competitiveness with other countries. This necessitates a highly educated, skilled workforce, inevitably leading to periodic educational reform (OECD, 2021). Decisions on education reform by governments around the world are often based on statistical records of students' improved attainment levels derived from standardised assessments, placing assessment at centre stage.

Governments tend to emphasise national standards-based assessment over teacher assessment, which is often viewed sceptically in terms of quality and consistency (Leung & Rea-Dickins, 2007). Concerns, particularly in debates about teacher assessments supplanting standardised testing, include but are not limited to potential bias—for example, in relation to gender or socioeconomic status (Burgess, 2015), claims of grade inflation (Guardian, 2021) and disagreement among teachers regarding classroom assessment practices (Lopez & Pasquini, 2017). While variations exist across countries, governments frequently overlook the localised technical and pedagogical challenges faced by teachers. Many language teachers lack formal training in assessment design. Katz (2012) rightly points out that for many teachers, “assessment is often treated as an add-on to the primary focus of instruction, and as a source of information about the outcome of carefully planned classroom activities,” and their “decision as to whether or not to link instruction and assessment has already been made for them” (p. 69).

A new and pressing challenge in this landscape is the rise of Generative AI (GenAI), which is rapidly transforming the way language is produced, evaluated, and understood. GenAI tools (e.g., ChatGPT, Copilot, etc.) can generate fluent, coherent texts that mimic human writing, raising concerns about the validity of traditional language assessments. These tools blur the boundaries between original student output and AI-assisted writing, making it increasingly difficult to assess authentic language ability. As a result, educators and policymakers must reconsider assessment design, integrity protocols, and the very constructs being measured in language education (Harding, 2026). The integration of GenAI into educational contexts necessitates a reevaluation of assessment literacy, particularly among

teachers who may lack the necessary skills to navigate these emerging complexities (Cui et al., 2025).

In light of the ongoing education reforms in various national contexts worldwide, serious attention should be given to supporting English language teachers in improving their assessment practices (Harding & Kremmel, 2017; Inbar-Laurie, 2012; Taylor, 2009). This article aims to promote teachers' assessment literacy by describing and explaining the ABCs of validity in assessment with practical guidelines. The article addresses the issues of classroom assessment, introduces the concept of assessment literacy, and provides an overview of language assessment types in education. It then differentiates between psychometric and edumetric assessments before introducing the notion of validity. The article provides critical guidelines for enhancing validity in classroom assessment. We particularly unpack "psychometric validity", which has been highly influential in the fields of educational and language assessment.

TEACHER ASSESSMENT IN THE LANGUAGE CLASSROOM

For classroom teaching, assessing language ability and learning attainment is an integral part of the language teaching and learning process. Teacher-made assessments for gauging the attainment of student learning outcomes in relation to curricular goals and content coverage should be carefully designed. For English language teachers, many classroom decisions depend on the outcomes of language assessment practices, such as determining what students know and where they need support, either individually or collectively. For students, the ways in which their learning performance has been assessed may well influence their learning attention and motivation (Green, 2018; Poehner & Infante, 2017). In addition to assessments used in the classroom, students may also be required to take externally imposed, often mandatory, high-stakes assessments (e.g., state-wide or national assessments).

Throughout this article, the term 'assessment' is used in a broad sense to refer to the gathering of information about what students know and whether and how they can apply their knowledge (Bachman, 2004). A test is just one high-profile type of assessment that involves quantifying performance quality through the use of a scoring system (e.g., a rating scale or a machine scoring algorithm; Isaacs, 2016). However, there are many other kinds of assessments—that is, ways of systematically gathering information about students' learning through individual or a set of performances (e.g., portfolios, conferencing, presentations, interviews,

quizzes, etc.). In this article, we use the term 'tests' only when that is the prescribed form of assessment, at the exclusion of other forms of assessment. It is often used for decision-making that has the potential to affect test-takers' lives and may also have repercussions for other educational stakeholders, institutions, and, from a macro-level perspective, society at large.

The *Standards for Educational and Psychological Testing* (hereafter, the *Standards*; AERA, APA & NCME, 2014), which is updated in a new edition every few years, presents an evolving view of psychometric validity that can be viewed as the gold standard of the day; however, it is written for measurement and assessment experts and researchers (Pitts & Naumenko, 2016), so they can use it as a reference point to guide assessment development and use. It is not written for teachers and is not designed to engage teachers with the core concepts of psychometric validity. In education, the concept of validity in relation to assessment holds special significance for teachers to be aware of (Popham, 2017). This reinforces the need to make key psychometric concepts and orthodox contemporary thinking accessible to teachers.

TYPES OF LANGUAGE ASSESSMENT IN EDUCATION

Figure 1 presents a hierarchical structure of educational assessments, including classroom and external assessments. This notwithstanding, for the purpose of our discussion, it may be useful to define these types of assessments separately. However, we do acknowledge they need not *necessarily* be polarised in the way we have portrayed here. First, classroom assessment encompasses formative assessment, which focuses on assessment for and as learning (i.e., process-oriented assessments designed to foster learning), and summative assessment, which focuses on *assessment of learning* (i.e., outcome-oriented assessments).

Figure 1. Educational assessments within and beyond the classroom

¹ Externally imposed assessments may be administered inside or outside of the classroom.

In Figure 1, the word 'stakes' refers to the nature and level of impact or consequences of assessment use on test-takers. Classroom assessment includes a range of assessments:

- *Formative assessment* is used to check whether learning is 'formed' (e.g., through the use of questions, activities, presentations, quizzes, and so forth. Teachers can use this information to inform their teaching. Formative assessment is ongoing throughout the teaching period.
- *Summative assessment* is a summary of student performance, which is taken to be a proxy for learning, at the end of the course. The term 'summative assessment' is often used interchangeably with 'assessment of learning' because the purpose of such an assessment is to collect summarised information on student learning performance after the teaching and learning period has been completed. Midterm and final tests are summative assessments and are often known as achievement tests (whether students

have achieved the expected learning outcomes assessed by tests or examinations).

- *Assessment for learning* is often used interchangeably with the term formative assessment. However, it tends to be broader since teachers may not only focus on the learning outcomes that will be assessed. Some of the students' learning challenges or difficulties may not always be directly related to the learning outcomes (e.g., how to use the target language in everyday situations or beyond the test).
- *Assessment as learning* only differs from assessment for learning in that students are at the centre of this approach. It emphasises student autonomy in assessing their own learning as they move through the term. Students regulate and self-assess their own learning, monitor their learning progress and challenges, and work to resolve those challenges. To achieve this, however, teachers need to provide students with guidance on how to regulate and assess their learning. Approaches that integrate assessment as learning include dynamic assessment (see Poehner & Infante, 2017) and learning-oriented assessment (Turner & Purpura, 2016).

Notably, some forms of classroom assessment serve both formative and summative purposes. For example, an essay that counts for marks and receives a formal grade (summative) may be accompanied by feedback through the teacher's comments or reflections (formative) to help the student think more deeply about the topic, foster skill development, or enhance awareness-raising. Although classroom and external assessments, as illustrated in the second level of Figure 1, are sometimes depicted as being in opposition to one another, some integrated models of learning-oriented assessment show that they can operate in tandem to promote learning (Jones & Saville, 2016; Turner & Purpura, 2016) or have blurred boundaries (Fulcher, 2024).

In Figure 1, formative assessments and assessments for learning are often considered low-stakes because their effects on students' lives are low or temporary. Summative assessments are often considered medium- or high-stakes because their effects on students' lives can be impactful and more permanent (e.g., passing or failing a unit of study, grade records in academic transcripts, graduation, college or university admission; see Kunnan, 2018). It should be noted that decisions based on assessment of learning can be used both inside and outside the classroom, with consequences for various stakeholders (not just students). For

example, an institution may use student grades or results from an external standardised test to judge teachers' teaching effectiveness or decide on future school or program funding or surveillance (e.g., Gonzalez & Firestone, 2013).

Finally, Figure 1 illustrates that language teachers are often confronted with external, mandatory, and standardised assessments (e.g., national tests, standards-based assessments, school admission or university or college entrance examinations, commercial language proficiency tests). External, standardised tests are often influenced by measurement theory from the fields of psychometrics and educational measurement. This concerns not only the extent to which a test accurately and reliably assesses the information it claims to assess, but also the way test scores are inferred from learners' performance and faithfully and meaningfully capture learners' underlying language ability, which is the focus of the assessment (Newton & Shah, 2014). Assessment of learning, particularly in the form of external, standardised tests (as opposed to teacher assessments that relate to instructional targets), can sometimes clash with pedagogical goals and lead to a narrowing of the curriculum (e.g., teaching to the test; Phakiti & Isaacs, 2021).

PSYCHOMETRIC APPROACH TO LANGUAGE ASSESSMENT

The psychometric perspective aims to develop generalisable theories of the human mind, including aspects of students' knowledge and ability that are not directly observable but can be inferred from systematic, direct, or indirect observations of behaviour or performance. This perspective has substantially influenced the field of language assessment, with dominant theories of language proficiency centring on linguistic knowledge and the ability to deploy that knowledge (Bachman & Palmer, 2010). To infer proficiency level, assessment stimuli in the form of items or tasks are often used to elicit snapshots of language use behaviours, which, in turn, are used to infer underlying language abilities or other associated constructs of interest.

The notion *construct* in language assessment typically refers to an abstract or theoretical concept or trait that exists independently and is hypothesised to underlie learning behaviours or language productions, for example (Bachman & Palmer, 2010). Theories (where available) can be useful for identifying the nature of the construct to be measured. The types of language and social constructs that language teachers tend to be interested in are intangible and not directly observable, and hence, cannot be directly measured. However, they can be inferred

from systematic and careful observation (e.g., the use of multiple well-crafted assessment items and tasks to elicit performance).

Psychometrics has influenced large-scale standardised tests used for estimating language proficiency and for selecting and admitting people to jobs or programmes of study, for instance. In educational assessment, national or state-standardised educational tests are typically administered to students to assess their literacy and numeracy skills objectively. In some settings, the results are often compared across schools, school districts, and states.

Psychometric validity

The discussion above has touched on some concepts of validity as they pertain to assessment. The notion of validity relates to the meaningfulness of the insights that are obtained about an individual's language ability based on their performance, and, in turn, the resulting inferences that are made about what they know, can do, or their skill level (see Chapelle, 2012, 2021; Kunnan, 2018; Lissitz, 2009). Over the past several decades, the fields of psychometrics, educational measurement, and assessment have focused on defining and exploring validity and validation (i.e., generating evidence to demonstrate validity) through the use of various approaches and frameworks. There is, as yet, no consensus on what validity means and many different interpretations of the term exist (Phakiti & Isaacs, 2021). For example, as outlined below, there is a longstanding debate about whether validity is a property of the test and whether the consequences of test score use and interpretation should be considered separate from or integral to the concept of validity (see Newton & Shah, 2016). Through the contributions of several scholars, including Cronbach and Meehl (1955), Messick (1989), and Kane (1992), to name just a few, the definition of validity and guidelines for validation have evolved, including in different editions of the *Standards* (AERA, APA, & NCME, 2014).

Validity was formally defined in the psychological literature, which began describing assessments in the 1930s (Lissitz & Samuelsen, 2007). The classic definition of “the degree to which a test or examination measures what it purports to measure” (Ruch, 1924, p. 13) suggested that the original focus of validity theory was on the test itself. That is, validity was believed to be an inherent, static property of a test. This concept was widely adopted and unchallenged until the early 1950s. From the 1960s, the original view of psychometric validity gradually shifted by recognising that no human assessment method is perfect (e.g.,

observations of behaviours or performance are fallible). However, it can be refined through rigorous processes.

In the late twentieth century, Messick (1989) introduced the highly influential *unitary concept* of validity. He (1995) posited that “validity is not a property of the test or assessment as such, but rather of the meaning of the scores. These scores are a function not only of the items or stimulus conditions, but also of the persons responding as well as the context of the assessment” (p. 741). Built on Messick’s, validity is now considered in relation to the interpretation and use of test scores rather than being a property of the test itself (e.g., Chapelle, 2021; Kane, 2013). Echoing this, the current version of the *Standards*, AERA, APA, and NCME (2014) defines validity as “the degree to which evidence and theory support the interpretations of test scores for proposed uses of tests” (p. 11). The focus, thus, is not on any given test, but rather on how test scores are interpreted and how those inferences about ability are used to inform decision-making.

The 2014 version of the *Standards* also maintains that “statements about validity should refer to particular interpretations for specific uses” (p. 11), which implies that the context of test use should be considered in validation (i.e., the process of generating validity evidence for a given assessment). That is, when an established test that has undergone rigorous validation for a particular context and purpose is being proposed for use in a different context and/or for a different purpose than that for which it was initially intended, it needs to be validated for that new context and purpose (Kane, 2013).

Practical guide I

Consider validity as a multidimensional concept guided by the following points in sequence:

1. what is being assessed and how well can the assessment instrument do its job consistently and adequately for its intended purposes? To achieve this, teachers need to reflect on the steps they take in devising and using assessment methods (e.g., assessment instructions, conditions such as time allowance and test formats, and tasks or questions).
2. why is the assessment needed and what kind of inferences and decisions can be made on the basis of the assessment performance (e.g., test score)? For example, are students’ scores rank ordered and compared? Are their scores compared against a set of language criteria or learning outcomes?

3. what impact or consequences could the decision have on students (e.g., confidence, motivation, pass-fail, graduation, employment), on other educational stakeholders (e.g., parents, teachers), and on society at large (e.g., is the student suitable to perform a given job in terms of language proficiency and other factors)?

Types of psychometric validity

Figure 2 summarises common types of validity in assessment that language teachers should apply to develop and improve effective classroom assessment practice, each concept of which will be elaborated on below. While face validity is not considered part of psychometric validity, it is included at the end of this section because it is an intuitive concept that reflects stakeholders' impressions of validity.

Figure 2. Types of psychometric validity

Construct validity

Construct validity can initially be understood in relation to the definition of constructs. That is, teachers first query the extent to which an assessment accurately and adequately measures the underlying construct they are targeting (e.g., language proficiency, reading ability, grammatical knowledge). They then move beyond that to reflect on whether the inferences made as a result of test scores or observations are reasonable assumptions to make based on students' performance manifestations on the (often unobservable) construct being targeted.

Messick (1989) views construct validity as the most important type of validity, as it is overarching in that it encompasses the other types of validity described below. This is a widely held view in educational and language assessment. Two notions that are related to construct validity are:

1. *Construct-irrelevance variance*, which denotes the influence of one or more variables that are extraneous to an assessment that can unduly influence the resulting performance and/or scoring outcome (Messick, 1995). For example, an online speeded essay writing test for L2 Chinese students might confound essay writing ability with other factors, such as the ability to shift from an English keyboard to select Chinese characters. Therefore, the assessment might not only reflect how well test-takers can write due to their computer literacy, as reflected in the assessment criteria, but also their ability to type rapidly—a potential source of construct-irrelevant variance.
2. *Construct underrepresentation*, defined as insufficient or incomplete inclusion of relevant content, items or tasks for eliciting information about a student's ability in light of the focal construct (Messick, 1995). In a classroom setting, performance samples (e.g., tasks or items) must adequately represent all aspects of the curriculum to ensure comprehensive assessment. For example, a pronunciation construct and curriculum target individual vowel and consonant sounds, word stress, rhythm, and intonation. If an assessment that seeks to make inferences about students' pronunciation ability only formally assesses individual sounds, it is underrepresenting the pronunciation construct.

Content validity

Content validity refers to the inclusion of relevant, representative, and sufficient samples of student behaviours or performances in an assessment in a way that comprehensively samples from a wider content domain or curriculum. Thus, it has an inverse relationship with construct underrepresentation in that the more content validity is weakened, the more the assessment fails to represent its intended content domain. The selection of content and tasks could be informed by theory (e.g., regarding the constituent components of the focal construct), hypotheses, and/or curricular objectives. An assessment that elicits a range of behaviours comprehensively representing the domain to which the performance seeks to be extrapolated will produce better content validity than one that elicits fewer and less representative behaviours (i.e., a construct underrepresentation

scenario). To maximise content validity, teachers need to select an appropriate and sufficient number of items from the content domain to which the assessment is supposed to extrapolate; however, this can be challenged by practical constraints, such as limited time and student or test-taker fatigue. There should be test specifications detailing the relevant domain that should be sampled from when developing the test. This can then serve as a benchmark for evaluating task and content coverage.

Criterion-related validity

Criterion-related validity refers to the relationship between test scores and some established external measure, such as scores from another test thought to measure a similar construct or real-world performance in a relevant domain that the test scores aim to predict. Two types of criterion-related validity are distinguished.

1. *Concurrent validity* refers to the extent to which test scores are related to an external criterion—a well-established measure that reflects the same or a closely related construct. This criterion might be another test believed to assess a similar construct, or a real-world performance outcome that the test is intended to predict. When two test scores from equivalent test forms (based on the same specifications) taken by the same test takers are correlated, a strong positive correlation coefficient is obtained, providing evidence of strong reliability. If the test forms are administered concurrently, such a correlation may also reflect strong concurrent validity.
2. *Predictive validity* denotes the extent to which a test score can predict future behaviours or performance (e.g., language proficiency scores may be used as predictors of students' academic attainment; e.g., Isaacs et al., 2023). In classroom assessment, predictive validity may be examined by correlating midterm scores with final assessment scores (e.g., to examine the extent to which students who perform well in the midterm also perform well overall on the final, and vice versa).

There are some points to note when the criterion measure in a predictive validity study is some form of classroom assessment. Bonner (2013) emphasises that assessments developed by classroom teachers often fail to meet the quality standards necessary for effective criterion measures—that is, measures that accurately predict the language proficiency test in question. Moreover, because the test is administered to only a small number of students, outliers can skew the results. Conversely, there have been suggestions that a broader range of criterion

measures could be investigated in tandem, including potentially classroom assessments or teacher or student perceptions (Pearson, 2020). In other words, teacher assessments could complement other indices, with potential advantages to having more than one criterion measure.

Consequential validity

Consequential validity refers to the extent to which test developers and test users consider both the intended and unintended consequences of test use (and potential misuse) on individuals, institutions, and the wider society. The term consequential validity focuses on investigating the consequences of test score use and interpretation on stakeholders, institutions, and society at large (see Messick, 1989). This concept highlights the importance of critically examining how assessments impact stakeholders within the broader educational landscape and, to the extent possible, as educators and policymakers, taking steps to mitigate potential negative consequences.

In the teaching and learning arena, consequential validity is often realised in terms of washback. Washback refers to the influence of assessment on teaching and learning behaviours and foci, often in a classroom context (see Alderson & Wall, 1993, for a classic reference). Washback is more pronounced in high-stakes assessments and is often investigated in the context of changes to a test resulting from a change or even a wholesale reform of a test or assessment system (Kim & Isaacs, 2018). For example, a language proficiency test that, after not assessing speaking, introduces a speaking component in a new version of the test, may prompt classroom teachers to focus on speaking during instructional time, whereas previously speaking may have been sidelined (Wall & Horák, 2008). It could also spur school principals, students, and parents to demand greater speaking instruction, and in turn, introduce market opportunities for individuals and companies to offer out-of-hours tutoring for supporting speaking development (e.g., cram schools) or promote language exchanges. Teaching to the test and narrowing the curriculum to focus on test content and format, or, conversely, engaging in more communicative behaviours to prepare for a new interactional task type, are examples of possible washback effects—positive and negative washback, respectively. Positive washback tends to occur when an assessment task is authentic (i.e., is similar to what test-takers need to be able to do in a real-world scenario) and can promote language skills that can be retained and applied outside of the assessment context. Conversely, a test that requires test-takers to listen and repeat pre-recorded utterances, for example. In contrast, if an

assessment asks students to complete a conversation through multiple-choice questions, they will likely not have the opportunity to speak or improve their speaking skills during test preparation or the test itself, and are unlikely to be able to transfer that knowledge to real-life communicative situations — an example of negative washback. Teachers need to foster positive washback to the best of their ability, within the constraints of the assessment system they are working in (much of which will be out of their control). They need to find a balance between assessment-driven instruction that meets system and stakeholder pressures and providing rich learning opportunities to genuinely enhance a student's language proficiency beyond the test itself. It is worth noting that when a high-stakes assessment is involved, some focus on test-wiseness strategies or techniques for “cracking” the test is likely to receive emphasis (Bachman & Palmer, 1996). This can be a source of construct-irrelevant variance if, for example, a student performs well or poorly not because of their reading comprehension ability, but simply because they are a skilled multiple-choice test-taker.

Face validity

Face validity is not a component of psychometric validity because it is not empirically measured and has been de-emphasised in literature on assessment and validity over the past several decades (Bachman & Palmer, 1996). It, therefore, is not included in Figure 2. However, it is a concept that some teachers are familiar with and, hence, warrants a brief discussion here. Face validity refers to the appearance of an assessment that looks as if it is assessing what it claims to assess (i.e., it looks right; it appears as if it is measuring what it says it does) from the vantage point of test-takers—the most common group referred to in relation to this concept. However, other stakeholders could also potentially be panelled about their perceptions of an assessment in this regard. For example, administering a grammar test to students and using the resulting scores to infer their writing ability may have low face validity if test-takers are not convinced of the relevance of the test as a measure of writing. Brown and Abeywickrama (2010) rightly pointed out that if students feel an assessment is not assessing what it is supposed to, “this might affect their performance” (p. 35).

HOW TO ENHANCE LANGUAGE ASSESSMENT VALIDITY

In this final section, readers are invited to consider three overarching principles that may enhance the validity of language assessment practices, potentially for both assessment for learning and assessment of learning.

1. Ensure the alignment among the intended learning outcomes, teaching and learning activities, and assessment tasks. When the intended learning outcomes are specified and are not articulated too broadly, it is more apparent what the focus of classroom instruction and assessment should be. Any items or tasks that are formally assessed should be familiar to students or test-takers. Ideally, they will have learnt to engage in such language use or learning activities in the classroom without drilling or teaching to the test. Aligning curricular goals with instructional delivery and assessments is not successful without considering students' or test-takers' characteristics to inform assessment design. Without good alignment, various types of validity (e.g., construct, content and criterion-related validity) cannot be sufficiently and appropriately addressed.
2. Recognise and follow key stages of assessment development and use (see e.g., Bachman & Damböck, 2017; Green, 2020). Teachers need to be able to form teams to work together on developing or refining an assessment due to the various stages, outlined as follows:
 - a. The first stage is *planning*, including identifying the purpose of the assessment, focal construct, budget, human resources, and timeframe to complete. Planning allows a critical and realistic discussion of test development and of current limitations or challenges.
 - b. The second stage is *developing*, including writing up specifications for the overall assessment, which may involve different task or item types, and providing a blueprint of those tasks or item types. The assessment may, in part, be based on a needs analysis or appraisal of students' language use demands in real-world settings or in reference to curricular goals.
 - c. The third stage is *piloting*, including obtaining reviews of the assessment specifications from other stakeholders (e.g., teaching colleagues) and trialling items or tasks with other teachers or students that have similar characteristics to the target users.
 - d. The fourth stage is *administering* or actually deploying the assessment that was specified in the second (development) stage, taking into account any modifications that were made as a result of the third (piloting) stage. This includes implementing administrative procedures that take into account logistical matters (e.g., implementing proctoring

- to ensure smooth assessment delivery and mitigate cheating behaviours).
- e. The final stage is *scoring and decision making*, including using objective or subjective scoring and performance reporting to students, ideally including meaningful, developmental, and individualised feedback provision.
3. Actively continue professional development in relation to language assessment in the interest of improving assessment literacy or an understanding of the knowledge and principles that teachers need to perform assessment activities to the best of their ability (Inbar-Lourie, 2017). Several language assessment books, such as Bachman and Damböck (2017), Brown and Abeywickrama (2010), Fulcher (2024), Ockey (2024), and Green (2020) as well as articles in academic journals such as *Language Testing*, *Assessing Writing* and *Language Assessment Quarterly*, present key considerations in language assessment design supported by research findings. These resources discuss ways to enhance the validity of assessments used in classroom settings, among other things. They also help teachers become more critical consumers of assessment and curricular materials, for example, in critically appraising a test provider's claims about what they are measuring, at what target proficiency level (and claims about CEFR alignment often should not be taken at face value), and how they go about doing so. We recognise that some of these resources require purchase or are behind a paywall requiring a subscription.

Even when accessed, journal articles may be written in a way that is conceptually inaccessible to teachers (Marsden & Kasprowicz, 2017). Open Accessible Summaries in Language Studies (OASIS), an open access digital resource (Marsden et al., 2018), are one-page accessibly written summaries of key research findings from journal articles in applied linguistics, including *Language Testing*, which encourages authors to craft a summary of their study once their article has been accepted for publication for uptake by a wider audience, including language teachers. Although relatively few assessment-specific articles are available, compared to other areas in applied linguistics (e.g., second language acquisition, psycholinguistics), those that do exist are an excellent, time-efficient way for teachers to engage with research. Summaries may be provided in multiple languages, including sign language, and some journals encourage or even require author engagement with them.

There is growing evidence that such summaries have the potential to widen outreach and engagement while also improving citation metrics (McKinley et al., 2025).

In some cases, OASIS summaries also link to open-access research instruments or tools that may also be teacher-relevant. For example, Isaacs et al.'s (2018) OASIS summary charts the development of a formative assessment tool for English for Academic Purposes teachers, focusing on international university students' English comprehensibility. A hyperlink to the tool with guidance for teachers on how to use it is available open access through the companion resource, the IRIS Repository of Instruments for Research into Second Languages (Marsden et al., 2016). OASIS is also collaborating with the new TESOLgraphics project, which summarises secondary research for teachers in a digestible format using infographics. Spoken abstracts and blogs are also becoming increasingly common to draw on a broader audience and make research more accessible. It is likely that, with the growing emphasis on open science in applied linguistics (Liu, 2023) and language testing (Kremmel & Isbell, 2024), there will continue to be an uptick in such sharing practices, particularly when funders or journals require or incentivise them.

Assessment methods, scientific knowledge, and technologies evolve, making it important to engage in continual and active updates to keep current. Consulting credible resources that promote ethical and fair language assessment practice is important. A few relevant resources include but are not limited to *Tools to Enhance Assessment Literacy (TEAL) for teachers of English as an additional language* (Tools to Enhance Assessment Literacy, 2025), the *ILTA Code of Ethics* (International Language Testing Association, 2018), which has been translated into several world languages, and ILTA guidelines for practice (International Language Testing Association, 2024), and Code of fair testing practices in education by the Joint Committee on Testing Practices (2004).

Another way to update knowledge in language assessment is to take training through short courses or pre- or in-service teacher training programmes, participate in public seminar series on assessment often run through university research centres, which may be offered on-line for wider audience capture, or take part in a Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) by a credible and ideally well-established provider targeting teacher professional

development and assessment literacy (e.g., British Council). The Teachers' Assessment Literacy Enhancement (TALE) project is an example of an open access language assessment professional development resource for teachers (Tzagari et al., 2018). New test reviews published in the journal *Language Testing* are now available with open access, allowing stakeholders and the general public to view and download the critiques without restriction. The growing emphasis on open science in applied linguistics and higher education (Marsden, 2019) suggests that other tools and innovations are likely to emerge in the years to come.

4. Partially overlapping with the third point above, join the global online language assessment community. LTEST-L is an unrestricted listserv for language assessment researchers and practitioners, including teachers from around the world with an interest in language assessment. Postings include substantive discussions of current issues in language assessment, which teachers sometimes initiate regarding practical matters, in addition to language assessment job advertisements, workshops, training courses, conferences, and announcements of field-relevant funding opportunities or prizes. Membership in professional language assessment associations, many of which host conferences, is another way to stay informed about activities and engage in networking. Although some organisations, such as ILTA, charge membership fees, several ILTA-affiliated regional associations currently offer free membership (e.g., ALTAANZ in Australia/New Zealand, EALTA in Europe, AALA in Asia, etc.) and are eager for member engagement (Taylor, 2026).

CONCLUDING REMARKS

This article aims to provide an accessible, theoretically informed discussion of psychometric validity, its implications for teachers, and strategies for further developing understanding and shaping practice. Assessment is not only at the centre stage of classroom teaching and learning but is part of a broader educational ecosystem. It ideally needs to be tailored for particular assessment needs and contexts and evaluated for those specific uses and contexts (Kane, 2013). We hope that language teachers reading this article will now have a practical understanding of what psychometric validity is and can see how the principles could apply to teacher-developed assessments and to critically evaluating external, often standardised language assessments.

Practical guide II

1. Develop a blueprint or plan that specifies the language skills or learning outcomes to be assessed and how they are to be assessed. This is similar to designing a house before actually constructing it, using a robust, well-thought-out plan with sufficient detail of what the house will look like once it is built.
2. Produce items or tasks to elicit enough evidence of meaningful performance or ability from the curricular targets or intended learning outcomes being sampled to avoid errors of reliance on a single item type that could increase the probability of chance findings. Where possible, elicit multiple snapshots of performance using a variety of methods, which should provide a more solid basis for making deductions about a learner's language ability.
3. Develop clear and transparent instructions for students to follow that are ideally as succinct as possible while being comprehensive enough to inform learners about what they need to do unambiguously. Details such as mark allocation, planning time/time on task, among others, should be provided. Clear administrative procedures and instructions can mitigate misunderstandings and ensure fairer practices for all.
4. Consider the consequences that interpreting the test scores and making decisions on that basis will have on students and other stakeholders. If the decision is high-stakes or impactful, more effort, time, and ideally resources and rigour will be needed for test development, preparation, and decision-making processes.

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AUTHOR

Talia Isaacs is Professor of Applied Linguistics and TESOL and Head of Research in her department at the UCL Institute of Education, University College London and co-editor of the international refereed journal *Language Testing*. Her research interests in language assessment are eclectic, including both standardised assessments and developing pedagogically-oriented tools to help learners calibrate views about their own performances through feedback provision. She has designed or led modules in applied linguistics and language assessment at universities in the UK, the US, and Canada and regularly disseminates her work to international audiences. Her collaborative research on assessment has been featured in various media sources, including Times Higher Education, The New York Times, the Canadian Broadcasting Corporation, and BBC Local Radio.

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